

Synthesis of some new 2-mercaptobenzothiazolyl-2-oxoazetidines as antimicrobial and anthelmintic agents

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Several 2-(arylidénylamino)-5-[(2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4) and 1-[5'-{(2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl}-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-substituted-3-chloro-2-oxoazetidines (5) have been synthesized and tested for their antibacterial, antifungal and anthelmintic activities. Structure of the compounds have been elucidated on the basis of their elemental analyses and spectral data.

2-Mercaptobenzothiazoles¹ and thiadiazoles² are known to possess various biological activities. Hence, it was thought of interest to synthesize some new 2-mercaptobenzothiazoles with pendent 1,3,4-thiadiazole and evaluate their antifungal, antibacterial and anthelmintic activities.

Results and discussion

Condensation of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with ethyl chloroacetate in dry acetone yielded ethyl-2-(benzothiazolylthio)-acetate (1). Compound 1 on the treatment with thiosemicarbazide afforded [(2-benzothiazolylthio)acetyl]-thiosemicarbazide (2). Dehydrative annulation of 2 with H₂SO₄ followed by NH₃ treatment gave 2-amino-5-[(2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3) which on condensation with various aromatic carbonyls yielded 2-(arylidénylamino)-5-[(2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-n). The β-lactam moiety in 4 was introduced by the cycloaddition of (4a-n) chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine to give 1-[5'-{(2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl}-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-4-substituted-3-chloro-2-oxoazetidines (5a-n) (Scheme 1). Purity of the compounds was monitored by TLC.

Compounds 4 and 5 were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherchia coli* (*Ec*), *Shigella dysenteriae* (*Sd*) and *Streptococcus aureus* (*Sa*) at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations and for antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* (*An*), *Candida albicans* (*Ca*) and *Rizopus oryzae* (*Ro*) at 10, 50 and 100 ppm concentrations by filter paper disc method³. Antibacterial streptomycin and antifungal griseofulvin were used as standards. The following compounds were found active against the noted bacteria : 4e (*Ec*, *Sd*), 4f (*Ed*, *Sd*, *Sa*), 4g (*Ec*, *Sd*, *Sa*),

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) CICH₂COOC₂H₅, (ii) NH₂NHCSNH₂, (iii) H₂SO₄/liq. NH₃, (iv) R₁COR₂, (v) CICH₂COCl/(C₂H₅)₃N.

4h (*Ec, Sd, Sa*), **4m** (*Ec, Sd, Sa*), **5e** (*Ec, Sa*), **5f** (*Ec, Sd, Sa*), **5g** (*Ec Sd, Sa*), **5h** (*Ed, Sd, Sa*), **5m** (*Ec, Sa*). The following compounds were found active against the fungi : **4e** (*An, Ca, Ro*), **4f** (*An, Ca, Ro*), **4g** (*An*), **4h** (*An, Ro*), **4m** (*An*), **5e** (*An*), **5f** (*An*), **5g** (*An, Ro*), **5h** (*An, Ca, Ro*).

Compounds **4** and **5** were screened for anthelmintic activity against the experimental infection of *Ancylostoma ceylanicum* in hamsters and *Hymenolepis nana* in young male rats by the method of Steward⁴. Mebendazole was used as a standard drug which killed 100% of *A. ceylanicum* at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg \times 3 and 100% worms were cleared up in *H. nana* infection at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg. The following compounds were found active against the helminthes : **4d-h**, **5e-h** and **5m**.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillaries. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer (200 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plates and was satisfactory.

Ethyl 2-(benzothiazolylthio)acetate (**1**) : Equimolar solution of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (0.1 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in dry acetone (40 ml) in the presence of anhyd. K₂CO₃ (5 g) was refluxed on a water bath for ~16 h. The solvent was then removed *in vacuo* and the residue crystallized from chloroform, 79%, m.p. 57–59°, ν_{\max} 3025, 1518, 1108, 1075, 1031, 636 (aromatic ring), 1719 (C=O of ester), 1610 (C=N), 1220 and 1040 (C–O–C), 715 (C–S–C) and 2912, 2875, 1427 and 710 cm⁻¹ (CH₂ and CH₃); δ 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.15 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.40 (2H, s, S-CH₂) and 6.72–7.94 (4H, m, Ar-H).

[(2-Benzothiazolylthio)acetyl]-thiosemicarbazide (**2**) : Addition of ethyl (2-benzothiazolylthio)-acetate (0.071 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.07 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h. It was cooled, concentrated and filtered. The product was recrystallized from chloroform, 70%, m.p. 181–183°; ν_{\max} 3350 (NHNH₂), 1130 (C=S), 1660 (CONH) cm⁻¹; δ 4.55 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 6.60–7.85 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.30 (4H, m, NHHCSNH₂).

2-Amino-5-[2-(benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**3**) : Compound **2** (0.05 mol) with conc. H₂SO₄ (16 ml) was kept overnight at RT. It was then diluted with 100 ml ice cold water and the excess acid was neutralized with liquid ammonia. The product so

obtained was recrystallized from chloroform : methanol mixture 74%, m.p. 209–210°; ν_{\max} 3355 (NH₂); 1600, 1440, 1305, 1172 and 700 cm⁻¹ (C=N and thiadiazole nucleus); δ 4.20 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.45 (2H, s, S-CH₂) and 6.75–7.93 (4H, m, Ar-H).

2-(3-Nitrobenzylidenylamino)-5-[2-benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**4a**) : Compound **3** (25 mmol), 3-nitrobenzaldehyde (25 mmol) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) were refluxed in methanol on a water-bath for ~5 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the solid thus obtained was recrystallized from chloroform, 70%, m.p. 224–226°; ν_{\max} 1590 (N=CH), 1510 and 1340 cm⁻¹ (Ar-NO₂); δ 4.45 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 4.80 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.73–7.91 (8H, m, Ar-H).

Other compounds **4b-n** were synthesized in a similar manner using various aromatic carbonyls.

1-[5'-[(2-Benzothiazolylthio)methyl]-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2-yl]-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-3-chloro-2-oxoazetidine (**5a**) : Compound **4a** (5.0 mmol) and triethylamine (10.0 mmol) and stirred well. To this solution chloroacetyl chloride (10.0 mmol) was added dropwise at 0–5°. The reaction mixture was stirred for ~4 h and the separated amine hydrochloride was filtered off. The filtrate was refluxed for ~2 h and the separated solid was recrystallized from methanol, 72%, m.p. 240–242°; ν_{\max} 1760 (C=O), 760 (C–Cl) cm⁻¹; δ 4.10 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, N-CH), 5.00 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, CHCl), 4.42 (2H, s, S-CH₂), 6.73–7.85 (8H, m, Ar-H). The compounds **5b-n** were synthesized from **4b-n** in a similar manner.

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